

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, R. Chelsea Nagy, & Alison K. Post

Rusty Red Waters in Madagascar
(Credit: NASA Image of the Day)

Quick Updates

- Chelsea Nagy gave a talk for the [Center for Social and Environmental Futures](#) describing the purpose and mission of Earth Lab & ESIL
- Earth Lab & ESIL attended the [Broader Impacts Network](#) Expo at CU Boulder to learn about and interact with other centers on campus
- Elsa Culler gave a Geography Colloquium: [Towards Earth Data Science for Everyone \(or, how I stopped worrying about developing global models and learned to love the local\)](#)
- Cibele Amaral was part of a team that published a report on [Tipping points in the biosphere](#)
- Amy Churchill, Assistant Professor of Ecosystem Science at Binghamton University, hosted a workshop on [Dissecting the Interview](#) during our EDS Seminar
- Several Earth Lab team members gave presentations at the American Geophysical Union (AGU) conference in San Francisco
- NC RISCC hosted the first of three [Ecological Transformation workshops](#)
- James Rattling Leaf Sr gave a seminar about [Utilizing Cultural Intelligence to advance Tribal engagement and partnership](#)

Research Abroad

Over the past few months, several of our team members traveled abroad for their research. Cibele Amaral visited Biosphere 2 in Tucson, Arizona, and Matt Rossi conducted research in South Africa. See their stories below.

Cibele visits the Biosphere 2!

ARID leadership team visiting Biosphere 2.

"It was a great experience to visit Biosphere 2 and get involved in such a great project, discussion, and team."

"Drylands represent 41% of the Earth's land surface and need groundbreaking research to support decisions that keep drylands providing ecosystem services under future climate scenarios," said Cibele.

Cibele Amaral, Interim Earth Lab and ESIL Analytics Director, joined the ARID team at [Biosphere 2](#) (the world's largest controlled environment dedicated to understanding the impacts of climate change, located in Tucson, AZ), in late October. The team is working on a new NASA Terrestrial Ecology scoping study called Adaptation and Resilience of Drylands (ARID). ARID is an initiative that aims to unite dryland scientists, stakeholders, and experts in remote sensing to propose a future NASA field campaign focused on improving our comprehension of drylands through integrated measurements across various spatial scales.

The project kick-off meeting focused on community engagement by hearing stakeholders' needs and advertising the project to the general public. The meeting took place at the University of Arizona, with dozens of stakeholders joining in person, and hundreds of people joining the webinar in the afternoon.

For the remaining 3 days, the leadership team met in Biosphere 2 to discuss stakeholders' needs, main themes of the scoping study, sub-teams for the study, and outreach actions for 2024.

Learn more & get involved: <https://aridscoping.arizona.edu/>.

Matt & Meghan visit South Africa!

In December, Matt Rossi (Research Scientist) & Meghan Hayden (Graduate Research Assistant) traveled to South Africa for their BioSCape research project. BioSCape is a NASA project focused on monitoring biodiversity using remote sensing and field observations. To this end, NASA recently conducted an airborne campaign in the Greater Floristic Region of South Africa in coordination with ~20 hypothesis-driven research projects.

The University of Colorado is leading a project called "Biodiversity Across Scales: Mapping Taxonomic, Phylogenetic, and Functional Diversity with eDNA, Field Surveys, and Remote Sensing Data." Along with collaborators at the University of California-Santa Cruz and the University of California-Merced and several South African partners, the team conducted field surveys and collected environmental DNA at select locations in the Eerste and Berg River watersheds in late October/November. These data will serve as the basis for understanding how local measures of biodiversity relate to biodiversity metrics derived from hyperspectral (UV-VIS-NIR-SWIR) data. For more info visit: <https://www.bioscape.io/science>.

Meghan Hayden collects a water sample for environmental DNA analysis.

The team visited over 30 sites along the Eerste and Berg River systems where they collected eDNA samples from soil, sediment, and water. They also collected benthic macroinvertebrates, conducted vegetation plot surveys, and assessed river morphology.

Headwaters of the Berg River

The field team heads out to one of the less disturbed sites in this biologically rich and unique fynbos ecosystem.

This was the team's second field season, which was coordinated with the BioSCape airborne campaign in order to have ground measurements contemporaneous with the remote sensing data.

ESIL Hackathon

From November 15-17, 50 Environmental scientists, data analysts, and AI experts from academia, non-profits, and the public sector came together under one digital roof to collaborate and provide solutions to on-the-ground needs at ESIL's first Hackathon, "Environmental MosAlc." The winning team received a financial award to meet in Boulder, CO (via ESIL's working groups), as well as cyberinfrastructure, technical, and scientific support to complete their project.

Visit [our website](#) for more information and details about past trainings and upcoming events.

New Team Member

Earth Lab is growing! Since our last newsletter, we welcomed a new Post-Doc who is working on wildfire entrapment risk. See our introductory Q&A session with Nicole!

Nicole Hemming-Schroeder is a Postdoctoral Associate for Earth Lab

1. What is your background?

I hold an M.A. in Applied Mathematics and Ph.D. in Earth System Science. Most recently, I worked on mapping and modeling individual tree mortality in the Sierra Nevada after a severe drought using high-resolution lidar and multispectral data.

2. What are you most looking forward to in your new position?

I am most looking forward to working with folks in Earth Lab and investigating questions related to wildfire spread.

3. What is your favorite national park?

I haven't been to many national parks, but I really enjoyed visiting Channel Islands National Park. The tiny foxes running around are adorable, and kayaking in the sea caves with a guide there was an amazing experience.

Team Social Events

This quarter, Earth Lab hosted two social events to gather staff, post-docs, and affiliates together for fall and winter celebrations. In October, over 20 people joined us in pumpkin painting, a baked-goods potluck, and themed activities for our Fall Festival.

In December, we hosted a WinterFest which included a cookie exchange, crackling digital fireplace, and crafting snowflakes to decorate the suite for winter.

Watch our Instagram highlight to see more.

